

A study on agglomeration behavior of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria nanopowders prepared by co-precipitation route[†]

Nityanand Chaubey and M. C. Chattopadhyay^{a*}

Fuel Cell Materials Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : mcc46@rediffmail.com, nchaubey_au@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 27 January 2011, accepted 04 February 2011

Abstract : In this study nano-crystalline ceria and 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria with cubic fluorite structure have been synthesized by co-precipitation method using solutions of cerium nitrate and gadolinium nitrate and liquor ammonia as a precipitating agent. Phase purity, lattice parameter and average crystallite size of the samples was determined by X-ray diffraction technique. The average crystallite size achieved by this method is 6 nm which is smaller than that of prepared by other methods. The presence of impurities and thermal decomposition behavior of the samples were investigated by Fourier transformed infra red spectroscopy and thermo gravimetric analysis/differential thermal analysis respectively. The particle size distribution of the samples was investigated by small angle X-ray scattering studies. Ethanol and octanol has been used for washing the precipitates in order to lessen the strength of hydrogen bonds between the neighboring precipitates and to get soft agglomerates with uniform particle size distribution. The microstructure of the sample was studied by Scanning electron microscopy.

Keywords : Gadolinia doped ceria, co-precipitation, agglomeration, X-ray diffraction, Small Angle X-ray scattering.

1. Introduction

In SOFCs, anode and cathode as well as electrolytes are mixed oxides. Usually they work at the temperature range of 900–1000°C. However, such a high temperature often leads to reactions between components, thermal degradation or thermal expansion mismatch. Efforts are on to synthesize and characterize such mixed oxides which can produce electricity at lower temperature range 600–800°C, thus reducing material fabrication problems and improve cell reliability during prolonged operation.

Cerium oxide and its doped composition with rare-earth oxides are one of the most important ceramic materials. It has been used as an ionic conductor, as a gas sensor and as an electrolyte of solid oxide fuel cells. Pure ceria has a fluorite type crystal structure with space group Fm3m. It does not undergo any crystallographic change from room temperature up to its melting point (~2973 K). Pure ceria is a poor oxide conductor. Ceria forms solid solution with oxides of different rare earth elements over a wide range of composition¹. These changes are interesting when tetravalent cerium ions in fluorite lattice are substituted with a trivalent dopant ion and in turn

oxygen vacancies are created in the anionic sublattice, for balancing the charge². Properties of these defects resulting from atomic substitution depend on the nature of dopant as well as on its mole fraction within the host lattice. When a Ce⁴⁺ ion is replaced with 2⁺ or 3⁺ cations, anion vacancy is created to compensate charges in the lattice. As a result, a solid electrolyte with predominantly ionic conductivity for oxygen over an extended temperature and oxygen partial pressure range is produced. The defect reaction for Gd³⁺ doped ceria can be written in Kroeger-Vink notation as :

The ionic conductivity in the doped ceria³ is due to oxygen ion vacancies (V_o). It has been found that Gd³⁺ or Sm³⁺ doped ceria have the highest conductivity^{4,5}. In Sm³⁺ doped ceria, 20 mol% Sm³⁺ have the highest conductivity^{6,7}. Although the exact composition of the CeO₂-Gd₂O₃ system that has the maximum conductivity is still not clear^{8,9}.

It has been found that in comparison to bulk powder, nanocrystalline powders show better sinterability and

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

greatly modified optical, electronic, catalytic and magnetic properties^{10,11} due to the extremely small crystallite dimension. The nanocrystalline materials give better phase homogeneity and have low sintering temperature which in turn affects the processing of material and decides the microstructure of the ceramic sample. Besides the large surface area that increases the driving force for sintering, nano-sized powders boost sintering at lower temperature¹². This is due to fact that smaller particle size allows densification to go on via grain-boundary diffusion instead of lattice diffusion. The flux of atoms along a grain boundary, J , may be written as

$$J = MC \nabla \mu \quad (2)$$

where M is the atomic mobility along the grain boundary, C is the vacancy concentration and $\nabla \mu$ (the gradient in the chemical potential between the particle necks and a free surface) is the driving force for sintering. Gadolinia or samaria doped ceria shows higher ionic conductivity at lower temperature (500–700°C) as compared to the presently used yttria stabilized zirconia (YSZ) which has sufficient ionic conductivity only around 1000°C. In the last few years nanosized doped cerium oxide has attracted a lot of interest as a solid electrolyte for solid oxide fuel cells due to its high ionic conductivity at lower temperature. This is based on the assumption that large area of interface in nano-sized materials may provide fast ionic conduction pathways leading to its high conductivity^{13,14}. Several methods have been used to prepare ceria based materials such as solid state reaction^{15,16}, glycine-nitrate process¹⁷, thermal evaporation technique¹⁸, sol-gel method¹⁹, citrate-nitrate auto ignition process²⁰, self propagating room temperature synthesis²¹, hydrothermal method²², urea formaldehyde polymer gel auto combustion process²³, co-precipitation method^{24,25} and mixed fuel process²⁶. The above methods have one general shortcoming of producing an inhomogeneous powder with large particle size.

The electrolyte in the SOFCs must be impervious to both fuel and oxidant to prevent gas mixing. The function of electrolyte is to carry the ions produced at one electrode to the other in order to balance the flow of current in the external circuit. The electrolyte material should be highly dense. In order to get dense electrolyte, the reduction of agglomeration behavior of electrolyte material is essential otherwise we will get electrolyte with low sin-

tered density with inhomogeneous microstructure which will reduce the conduction behavior of electrolyte to a great extent.

Agglomeration is of two types – soft agglomeration and hard agglomeration. Soft agglomeration is due to van der Waals force and the high curvature of the surface of the small particles and this agglomeration can be removed by ball-milling of the product and does not have much effect in the sintering process. The hard agglomeration is created due to formation of chemical bonds between the precipitate particles. This agglomeration affects the sintering process since it can not removed by applying outside force. During the precipitation process water molecules bridges the hydroxyl groups present on the surface of adjacent precipitates and yields hard agglomerates by forming actual bonds when the hydroxide converts into the oxide²⁷. Hence alcohol is used as a post precipitation washing medium^{28–30} to inhibit the agglomeration and formation of aggregates which generally takes place during the calcination process at higher temperatures.

In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesize nanocrystalline ceria and 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria (GDC20) powders with uniform particle size distribution with average crystallite size less than 10 nm and having large surface area, by co-precipitation method followed by washing with different solvents and the effect of post precipitation washing solvent on the properties of powders have been studied. Ethanol and octanol has been used for washing the precipitates in order to lessen the strength of hydrogen bonds between the neighboring precipitates and to get soft agglomerates with uniform particle size distribution.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. FTIR results

The FTIR spectra of the precursors are shown in Fig. 1. It has been used to detect the certain functional impurities present in the samples prepared. A broad absorption band in the region of 3200 cm⁻¹ to 3600 cm⁻¹ is due to the O-H stretching vibration of absorbed water or hydroxyl group in the alcohol. The absorption peak at 1595 cm⁻¹ is due to bending vibration of water molecule. Dissolved or atmospheric CO₂ was indicated by the band located at around 2350 cm⁻¹ (stretching vibration) and 1350 cm⁻¹ (bending vibration). Trace amount of nitrate ions was indicated by

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of precursors obtained (A) CeO₂ washed with octanol, (B) GDC20 washed with octanol, (C) GDC20 washed with ethanol and (D) GDC20 washed with water.

the bands located around 1400 cm⁻¹ and 1030 cm⁻¹. N-H stretching vibration occurred at 3150 cm⁻¹ but could not be seen due to accumulation with O-H stretching vibration. The absorption peak at 840 cm⁻¹ is supposed due to bending mode of N-H. A band located in the area from 400 to 760 cm⁻¹ is due to stretching vibration of CeO₂.

2.2. Thermal analysis results

The TG-DTA pattern of the GDC20 precursors is shown in Figs. 2 and 3 which shows the typical decomposition behaviors of precursors. From the TGA result it

Fig. 2. TG/DTA results of GDC20 precursor washed with water.

Fig. 3. TG/DTA of GDC20 precursor washed with octanol

can be seen that about 75% of the total weight loss occurred in the temperature range of 50–300°C and rest of the weight loss occurred up to 1000°C. Weight loss in the range of 50–200°C is due to the loss of chemically adsorbed water. Weight loss above 200°C is supposed due to decomposition of precursor to oxides with the evolution of O₂, NO₂, NH₃ and H₂O. The results of DTA consists large endothermic peak around 150°C in the case of sample obtained with washing with water and relatively small endothermic peak around 130°C in the case of samples washed with ethanol and octanol. These peaks

correspond to vaporization of water from the samples. Relatively small peak in the case of samples washed with ethanol and octanol is supposed due to replacement of water by the alcohol during the washing. An exothermic peak in DTA result around 200°C is due to decomposition of precursor to oxides and formation of solid solution of Gd₂O₃ doped ceria which is also supported by XRD results.

2.3. X-Ray analysis and crystallite size results

The synthesized powders were calcined in air at various temperatures to investigate the evolution of crystalline phases. The Fig. 4 shows the XRD spectra for powders obtained by co-precipitation method followed by

after heating the samples at 600°C for 6 h there is little effect on the peak width and intensity indicating little change in crystallite size. However, from Fig. 7. and 8 it can be seen that after heating at 950°C and further at 1200 °C the peak width becomes very narrow and intense, indicating rapid increase in the growth of the crystallite size. After calcinations in air at different temperatures up to 1200°C, 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria samples were single phase and face centered cubic crystal system with space group Fm3m and lattice parameters $a = b = c = 5.4117 \text{ \AA}$ (ICDD, PDF=340394).

The average crystallite size was determined by the well known Scherrer relation which shows that nanocrystalline samples of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ce-

Fig. 4. XRD results of GDC20 samples obtained after washing with water (A), ethanol (B), octanol (C) and calcined at 80°C

washing with different medium, which shows that the initial crystallization into cubic fluorite structure takes place after heating for 12 h at 80°C. This is very low temperature for fluorite structure formation. Fig. 5 shows the XRD patterns of CeO₂ obtained after washing in octanol and calcined at 900°C for 5 h. It has an average crystallite size of 12 nm. From the Fig. 6 it can be seen that

ria were produced from this method. The average crystallite size for the octanol washed sample was 6 nm compared to 7 nm and 8 nm for the ethanol and water washed samples respectively. This means that weaker interaction between the precipitates occurred by washing it with octanol and ethanol. From the Table 1, it can be seen that after heating at 600°C the crystallite size of the powder

Fig. 5. XRD patterns of CeO₂ obtained after washing with octanol and calcined at 900°C for 5 h

Table 1. Effect of post precipitation washing solvent on average crystallite size of GDC20 samples after heat treatment at different temperature

Temperature (°C)	Average crystallite size (nm)		
	Water washed	Ethanol washed	Octanol washed
80	8	7	6
600	11.3	10.7	7
950	18.92	15.46	13.50
1200	48.60	47.10	43

obtained after washing with octanol is 7 nm, while in the case of powders obtained after washing with water and ethanol it goes to 11.3 nm and 10.7 nm respectively. It shows that *in situ* agglomeration has taken place in the case of powders obtained after washing with water and ethanol due to hydrogen bonding between the precipitates while treating the gelatinous precipitate with octanol reduces the *in situ* agglomeration efficiently. The soft agglomeration in the case of powders obtained from octanol washing will also be confirmed by particle size distribution results obtained by small angle X-ray scattering technique. Theoretically, to get good sinterability the ceramic

powder should have particles with small size and uniform distribution. From the XRD analysis we see that the powders obtained after washing with octanol fulfill this condition to a large extent. XRD patterns also show that a single solid solution of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria is formed after heating as there are only peaks of CeO₂. Gadolinia doped ceria samples retained the cubic symmetry of CeO₂ ($a_0 = 5.4117 \text{ \AA}$) as the ionic radii of Gd (9.38 nm) is closer to that of Ce (8.7 nm). Thus, ceria fluorite structure dissolves 20% gadolinium oxide.

2.4. Particle size distribution

The particle size distribution is used to determine the agglomeration uniformity. Particle size and its distribution in ceramic powder affect the microstructure and consequently the conduction behavior of the ceramics. From Fig. 9, it is clear that the agglomeration is between 3 nm to 32 nm for sample obtained after washing with water, between 2 nm to 34 nm for those washed with ethanol and between 3 nm to 12 nm for sample obtained after washing with octanol. From the particle size distribution result, it is clear that the powders obtained after washing

Fig. 6. XRD patterns of GDC20 samples obtained after washing with (D) water, (E) ethanol, (F) octanol and calcined at 600°C for 6 h.

with water contains much hard agglomerates than octanol washed which has good uniformity. The shape of particles was assumed to be spherical. Thus it can be seen that agglomerate structure is affected by the washing solvent which has been used. Several reasons can be suggested for hard agglomeration. The capillary pressure arguments suggests that the surface tension of the washing liquid is responsible for hard agglomeration but it is not acceptable in the present case since the particles are on the order of 10 nm in size. Another reason can be solubility of particles in water and ethanol. During the drying of suspensions, the solute may reprecipitate between the particles and formation of bond between the particles leads to hard agglomerates but this effect will not prevail in this case as the solubility of hydroxides are

fairly low for both water and ethanol. In the end according to surface chemistry the hard agglomeration is due to hydrogen bonding between surface hydroxyl groups on the precipitates. During the drying and calcinations, the hydroxide is converted to the oxide and formation of hard agglomerate takes place due to formation of actual bond between the adjacent precipitates. The soft agglomeration in the powders obtained after washing with octanol is considered due to substitution of water with octanol by slowly heating the gelatinous precipitate in octanol. The long chain alcohol replaces the bridging water molecules between particles during heating process. Thus the close contact of the particles is prevented due to steric effect of octanol between the particles. This is reason why the treatment with octanol produces soft agglomerates. This

Fig. 7. XRD results of GDC20 samples obtained after washing with (G) water, (H) ethanol, (I) octanol and calcined at 950°C for 16 h.

Fig. 8. XRD results of GDC20 samples obtained after washing with water (J), ethanol (K), octanol (L) and calcined at 1200°C.

Fig. 9. Particle size distribution of GDC20 samples obtained after washing with water (B), ethanol (D), octanol (F) and calcined at 600°C

also explains the small crystallite size of powders obtained after washing with octanol than that of powders obtained after washing with water. Hard agglomeration in the case of powders obtained after washing with ethanol is due to the low boiling point of ethanol and its high miscibility with water, which prevents the complete replacement of water by ethanol during the washing and drying process. During ball-milling the hard agglomerates can not be completely broken down to produce uniform powders. As the densification starts, the densely packed regions density first, pull away from the surrounding regions and thus leave large pores, which inhibit complete densification during calcinations. However, the soft-agglomerated powders obtained after washing with octanol can be completely broken down during ball-milling and consequently does not impede densification.

2.5. Sintering behavior of GDC20 nanopowders

Several of the bulk properties are related to the sintered density such as electrical conductivity and thermal expansion behavior. Dense compositions show much higher total conductivity and lower activation energy³¹. The bulk densities of all these samples were calculated by measuring the final pellet dimensions. This method was

chosen over the traditional Archimedes Method because of the ease of measurement and relatively low error, < 2%, made possible by the uniformity of the sintered sample dimensions to within error limit ± 0.002 . Since 1673 K is the fabrication temperature of SOFCs, it is necessary to study the density of material sintered at this temperature. Theoretical density of the samples was calculated using the expression

$$d_{th} = z M / 0.6023 V \quad (3)$$

where, M (in atomic mass units) is the mass of one formula unit, Z is the number of such chemical units in one unit cell of the crystal and V (in \AA^3) is the volume of the crystalline unit cell as determined by XRD. The relative density was calculated by

$$\text{Relative density} = \left(\frac{\text{Measured sintered density}}{\text{Theoretical density}} \right) \times 100$$

As expected, the highest density (97% of theoretical density) was observed for the powders obtained after treating the precipitate with octanol due to its superior powder properties. The relative density obtained in this case is comparable to relative density obtained at relatively much higher sintering temperatures in the case of gadolinia doped ceria samples prepared by other methods^{32,33}. It is

believed that soft agglomeration and high surface area of this powder results in better packing at the green stage of the pellet which helps sintering in an articulated manner in comparison to other powders. The powder obtained after washing the precipitate in water gives the lowest sintered density (87% of theoretical density) due to the inferior quality since hard agglomerates are formed in this case. The powder obtained after washing the precipitate in ethanol gives the sintered density (91% of theoretical density) which is lower than the powders obtained after treating the precipitate with octanol. This is due to the fact that low boiling point of ethanol and its high miscibility prevents the complete replacement of water by ethanol during the washing and drying process and agglomeration takes place due to hydrogen bonding.

2.6. SEM results

Fig. 10 shows the microstructure of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria sample calcined at 600°C obtained after washing the sample with octanol. It shows that the powders are homogenous in nature. SEM micrograph shows that powders form loose agglomerates. The particles are bonded together due to weak van der Waals forces and also due to high curvature of the surface of the small particles, with no significant local sintering among the particles. This agglomeration can be removed by ball-milling of the product. The particles have nearly spherical shape.

Fig. 10. SEM micrograph of GDC20 sample obtained after washing with octanol and calcined at 600°C.

3. Experimental

(A) Sample preparation

Ceria and 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria samples were prepared from cerium nitrate hexahydrate (CDH, Bombay) and gadolinium nitrate hexahydrate (CDH, New Delhi). The stoichiometric amounts of cerium nitrate and gadolinium nitrate were dissolved in distilled water to make 0.15 M solutions. Hydrolysis of nitrates to hydroxides was done by adding into 4 M NH₄OH solution drop wise and keeping the pH > 10. A gelatinous precipitate was formed when the nitrate solutions were added into the NH₄OH solution. The obtained gelatinous precipitate was divided into three parts for further investigations. The first portion of this precipitate was washed with water several times while the second portion of the precipitate was washed with ethanol several times and the third portion of the precipitate was dipped in octanol, stirred by a magnetic stirrer and heated on a hot plate at 100°C. During the heating, octanol was added to the solution frequently to make sure that the water within the gel will be completely replaced by octanol. The samples were further calcined at higher temperature to get phase pure samples.

The formation of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria sample by co-precipitation method involves the following chemical reactions

(1) Dissociation of NH₄OH and metal nitrates

(2) Precipitation reactions :

(3) Thermal decomposition reaction and crystal formation :

where, (aq), (s) and (g) stands for aqueous, solid and gaseous state respectively.

(B) Physicochemical characterization

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded at room temperature using a spectrometer (FTLA, 2000, Make : ABB Ltd.) with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Pellets were prepared with 13 mm KBr die set by compressing an intimate mixture obtained by grinding 1 mg of the substance in 100 mg of KBr with mortar and pestle and applying an optimum pressure of 9 Ton using a 15 Ton hydraulic pellet press (Kimaya Engineeres, Thane). While preparing the pellets necessary precautions were taken to avoid moistures. The instrument calibration was confirmed by recording the spectra of standard polystyrene film. Powder X-ray diffraction data for the samples were collected on a Rigaku D-max 2000/JADE 6.0 copper rotating anode X-ray diffractometer using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation (1.54056 \AA) and using silicon as an external standard. The data were collected at a scanning rate of 1° per minute. The patterns were indexed to generate their lattice parameters using POWD program (version 2.2). The average crystallite size, D of the calcined powders was estimated from the broadening of XRD reflections using the Scherrer relation :

$$D = 0.9 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta_B \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the radiation used, β is the full width at half maximum (in radian) on two theta scales and θ_B is the Bragg's angle. High grade silicon powder was used as standard to account for instrument broadening correction. Thermal analysis was done on TG/DTA Equipment (SETRAM model 92-16.18) in air from room temperature to 1200°C with a heating rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Al_2O_3 was used as a reference material and the sample was kept in cylindrical platinum crucible. For particle size distribution, Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) experiments were performed on Rigaku RINTPC2000 using rotating anode X-ray generator operated at 40 kV and 40 mA in transmission geometry using radiation with wavelength of 1.54056 \AA in the region of small angle scattering $0.02\text{--}5^\circ$. The microstructure of powder samples was studied using both Optical microscope (GETNER SD-2PL) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Philips ESEM model XL 30.

4. Conclusion

Nanocrystalline powders of 20 mol% gadolinia doped ceria for intermediate temperature solid oxide fuel cell electrolyte have been synthesized by co-precipitation method using different post precipitation washing solvents. XRD study showed that the formation of crystalline phases in all the three powders takes place at relatively low calcination temperature of 80°C and the powders have face centered cubic structure (with space group $\text{Fm}\bar{3}\text{m}$). The average crystallite size of samples increases with calcination temperature. It has been found that the powders obtained after washing with water and ethanol produces hard agglomerates while those washed in octanol gives soft agglomerates. The washing with octanol after precipitation prevents interaction between particles and reduces the possibility of any chemical bonds forming between nanoparticles during drying and further calcinations to a great extent. This inhibits the formation of hard agglomerates and soft agglomerates are formed which leads to relatively high sintered density (97% of theoretical density) after sintering at 1400°C which is essential for novel electrolyte material for IT-SOFCs. Therefore, the selection of appropriate post precipitation washing solvent is necessary in co-precipitation method in order to inhibit the hard agglomeration and to get electrolyte material with higher sintered density.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge Nanophosphor Application Centre, University of Allahabad, Allahabad and Dr. Shyamala Bharadwaj, Chemistry Division, BARC, Trombay, Mumbai, for providing characterization facilities. One of the authors (Nityanand Chaubey) is also thankful to Dr. Preyas Ankit for his help in recording FTIR spectra.

References

1. V. Grover and A. K. Tyagi, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2004, 39, 859.
2. A. Nakajima, A. Yoshihara and M. Ishigame, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1994, 50, 13297.
3. J. A. Kilner and B. C. H. Steele, in : O. T. Sorensen (ed.), "Non-Stoichiometric Oxides", Academic Press, New York, 1981.
4. R. Gerhard-Anderson and A. S. Nowick, *Solid State Ionics*, 1981, 5, 547.

5. J. A. Kilner, *Solid State Ionics*, 1983, 8, 201.
6. H. Yahiro, E. Egushi and H. Arai, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 1998, 18, 527.
7. K. Egushi, T. Setoguchi, T. Inouse and H. Arai, *Solid State Ionics*, 1992, 52, 165.
8. G. B. Balazas and R. S. Glass, *Solid State Ionics*, 1995, 76, 155.
9. S. Dikmen, P. Shuk and M. Greenblatt, *Solid State Ionics*, 1999, 126, 89.
10. H. Weller, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Eng.*, 1993, 32, 41.
11. H. Gleiter, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 1991, 24, 79.
12. C. Herring, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1950, 21, 301.
13. S. Kim and J. Maier, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2002, 149, J73.
14. T. Suzuki, I. Kosacki and H. U. Andersen, *Solid State Ionics*, 2002, 151, 111.
15. Y. J. Leng, S. H. Chan, S. P. Jiang and K. A. Khor, *Solid State Ionics*, 2004, 170, 9.
16. B. P. Mandal, V. Grover, M. Roy and A. K. Tyagi, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2007, 90, 2961.
17. Y. Ji, J. Liu, T. He, L. Cong, J. Wang and W. Su, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2003, 353, 257.
18. W. H. Lee and P. Shen, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 2002, 166, 197.
19. X. Sha, Z. Lu, X. Huang, J. Miao, Z. Liu, X. Xin, Y. Zhang and W. Su, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2007, 433, 274.
20. S. Basu, P. S. Devi and H. S. Maiti, *J. Mater. Res.*, 2004, 19, 3162.
21. Z. D. Dohcevic Mitrovic, M. Grujic Brrjcin, M. Scepanovic, Z. V. Popovic, S. Boskovic, B. Matovic, M. Zinkevich and F. Aldinger, *J. Phys. Condns. Mater.*, 2006, 18, S 2061.
22. L. Lu, J. Tang, Y. X. Li, M. Guo, M. Zhang and X. Wang, *J. Nano Sci. Nanotechnol.*, 2007, 7, 2883.
23. M. Biswas, K. Prabhakaran, N. M. Gokhale and S. C. Sharma, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2007, 42, 609.
24. T. Mori, J. Drennan, Y. Wang, J. H. Lee, Ji-guang Li and T. Ikegami, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2003, 150, A. 665.
25. K. Higashi, K. Sonoda, H. Ono, S. Sameshima and Y. Hirata, *J. Mater. Res.*, 1999, 14, 957.
26. S. Banerjee and P. S. Devi, *J. Nanopart. Res.*, 2007, 9, 1097.
27. M. J. Ready, R. R. Lee, J. W. Halloran and A. H. Heuer, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1990, 73, 1499.
28. O. Vasylykiv and Y. Sakka, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 2001, 84, 2489.
29. M. S. Kaliszewsk and A. H. Heuer, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1990, 73, 1504.
30. E. N. S. Muccillo, S. K. Tadokoro and R. Muccillo, *J. Nanopart. Res.*, 2004, 6, 301.
31. X. Sha, Z. Lu, X. Huang, J. Miao, Z. Liu, X. Xin, Y. Zhang and W. Su, *J. Alloys Compd.*, 2007, 433, 274.
32. I. Reiss, D. Braunshtein and D. S. Tannhauser, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1981, 64, 479.
33. K. Q. Huang, M. Feng and J. B. Goodenough, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1998, 81, 357.

